

GHRSSST Connections with CEOS: SST-VC

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Session: Agency Reporting

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SST-VC recent activities

- SST Constellation Whitepaper finalized (Jan 2020)
 - But still not on CEOS website !
- Ed Armstrong took over as co-lead from Ken Casey in Oct 2019. Christo Whittle to succeed Anne O'Carroll in Oct 2020
- Co-leads participated in
 - Telecon with SIT chair and CEOS leadership (Dec 2019)
 - CEOS SIT 35 virtual meeting (Mar 2020)
 - SST VC report and contributions to CEOS COAST presentations on “ARD opportunities in Coastal and Ocean Domains”
 - Participated in various CEOS COAST telecons
 - CEOS Working Team all-hands webex (May 2020)
 - Presentation on ARD concepts to GEO Aquawatch webex (May 2020)

SST Constellation Whitepaper: “*Current and future sea surface temperature missions: Towards 2050*”

- Review of Key Points:
 - Report on the full spectrum of the SST lifecycle:
 - Measurements and radiometers
 - User needs, and science applications and impacts
 - Data management, open distribution and formats
 - Challenges related to:
 - Provision of Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM)
 - Longterm reference systems and methodologies
 - Improved data management, coordination, and distribution and GHRSSST data federation
 - Sustained continuity of passive microwave SST determination using a 6.9 GHz channel
 - AMSR3 and CIMR

SST-VC future activities

- Review and summarize the state of ARD across the Virtual Constellations
 - Focusing on data formats and metadata structures, variables, services for ARD implementation
 - Availability of uncertainty measurements, transformation capabilities, and data quality flagging
 - ARD storage, cloud optimization, and data recipes
 - Focus first on the SST and OC VC. Add other VCs to the review in the second half of the year.
 - Assess CEOS-COAST needs and support project implementation
 - Engage ARD efforts of other CEOS partners (e.g., land)
 - Identify current gaps and future improvements with regard to dataset interoperability across the interdisciplinary VC products
 - Report or review presentation by April 2021 or similar

Additional topics and themes

- More collaboration with other VCs on common themes, e.g. coasts
- Data management evolution
 - Provide recommendations for improving search relevancy and data access across CEOS VC partners (Ongoing work within GHRSSST)
 - Search relevancy / decision trees based on GHRSSST product search. This is likely to be built on through the GHRSSST activities
- Engaging early career scientists. To be conference theme at the 2020 GHRSSST ST meeting programme